

**HOW EMOTIONAL QUOTIENT AND SELF-COMPASSION AFFECTS
QUALITY HEALTHCARE SERVICES**

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ABSTRACT

Nursing personnel being an important part of the Healthcare team members has a major responsibility in providing the quality Healthcare services to the clients. Nurses has to be high emotionally quotient, self-compassionate and should have good communication skills in providing quality Healthcare services. Modern nursing demands skill of EQ to meet the need of direct patient care and cooperative negotiations with the multidisciplinary team members because these parameters are interrelated and strongly influence the nurses in delivering the services. People develop concern for compassion for the Welfare and well-being of others. Compassion includes a non-judgemental approach in responding to failure or mistakes.

Key Words: Self-Compassion, Emotional Quotient, Quality health care

Introduction:-

Nowadays quality care has become an important aspect in the development of Healthcare services. Patient satisfaction is the utmost priority. All Healthcare professional realise that the main beneficiary of Healthcare system is the client and it's a challenge for all the Healthcare professionals in India to find ways to make the client satisfied. The term patient satisfaction is rapidly changing to the customer satisfaction and the degree of patient satisfaction rate play an important role in the assessment of quality Healthcare provided. Due to modern advancement and technological change, Healthcare is growing very rapidly and patient's knowledge level about their right is also increased .They are more demanding as compared

to previous days and the hospital's staff required to meet their needs .So we can say that the important factors which can affect the patient satisfaction are haseless admission procedure, Diagnostic services ,employees behaviour , cleanliness, good nursing care ,food, communication ,interpersonal manner of the physicians , nursing personnel and other staff members technical services accessibility and convenience.

Objectives:-

The study was planned with the following objectives:

1. To find out the impact of self-compassion and Emotional Quotient of Nurses in quality patient care.
2. To explore about the components of Emotional and self -compassion

Methodology

Anextensiveliteraturereviewofsecondarydatasourceswasundertakenasrelevanttothe stated objectives of the study. In order to fill in secondary data gaps on topics such as of emotional quotient and self-compassion the data was obtained from secondary sources,a few research studies were also incorporated in the report.

Self-compassion and its Components

Self-compassion consists of the following three components self-kindness, perceptions of common humanity and mindfulness.

Self-kindness involves extending kindness into one-self instead of self-judgement and criticism, common humanity is also involved.

Compassion has been more simply defined as the emotion one experiences when feeling concern for another suffering and designing tool in hands that person's welfare. From this point of view compassion is considered to have two main roles. The effective feeling of caring for one who is suffering and the motivation to relieve that suffering.

When one practices compassion one's own happiness is enhanced. However person's self-negativity is an obstacle for developing compassion therefore it is very important to develop an awareness of greed, anger, false fixed beliefs and then overcome these emotions fully by replacing them with compassion.

Compassion helps the nurses in problem solving and decision making in dealing with the clients. If a nurse responds in a compassionate manner in providing care to the client than this compassionate approach improves the overall welfare of the clients as well as their relatives and the health team members.

Whenever we face failures in life or we are committing mistakes/ struggling in life, self-compassion is a source of support and friendship that is available when we need it most. Sometimes in life whenever we face failures or we are making mistakes or struggling in life self-compassion is a source of friendship and support that is available when we need it most.

Various research literatures suggested that the nurses have to be self-compassionate then only they can deliver the quality care to the clients. Another important aspect affecting the Healthcare service quality is the emotional intelligence of Healthcare personnel.

Emotional Quotient and its components:-

Literature suggested that the emotionally intelligent nursing staff deliver more qualitative services and perform beyond the patient's expectations and this automatically affects client's satisfaction.

From various research it has been inferred that the individual who have middle to high emotional intelligence are more likely to have professional success and increased job satisfaction. Emotional intelligence is the capacity of a person to understand the emotions and purposefully manage them. It is a competency for individuals to express their emotions and understand their own behaviour as well as the behaviour of others and obtain a sense of self-awareness as they achieved success in their life.

EQ accounts for 80% of success and Nursing profession requires a high degree of emotional quotient for example the nurses are expected to display emotions that convey caring understanding and sympathetic behaviour towards the clients and their family members.

Similarly, Henderson(2001) states that emotional involvement by nurses may give contribution to the quality Healthcare services because majority perceive emotional engagement as a requirement of excellence in nursing practice thus, we can say that emotions are not to be dismissed but rather have an important place in the quality of care .

Allen (2003) acknowledges that nursing personnel have ability to manage their own emotions and understand the patient's needs in providing the care. Modern nursing demands skill of EQ to meet the need of direct patient care and cooperative negotiations with the multidisciplinary team members. E.Q also helps to gain awareness and control of one's emotions in the workplace and show how to improve performance as well as professionally it can improve decision making by using one's heart and not just one's head.

Five areas of emotional quotient:-

1) Self-awareness 2) Self- regulations 3) Motivation 4) Empathy and 5) Social skills.

Self-awareness : The ability to recognise and understand your mood, emotions and internal drive as well as their effect on the other people example I'm aware of My Greatest strength and skills.

Self-regulation: The ability to control or redirect our destructible impulses and mood and ability to suspend judgement and thinking before acting example in stressful or 10 situations I keep myself calm and cool.

Motivation: Passion to work for reasons that go beyond monetary gains or status and the ability to pursue goals with energy and persistence. Example I seek out innovative ways of getting the tasks done and feel self-satisfied.

Empathy: - The ability to understand emotional makeup of other people for example: I can understand someone's true feelings based on their body language.

Social skills:- The proficiency in managing relationships and building networks example I find it easy to establish common ground with somebody I have just met.

Emotional quotient plays a pivotal role in building mental health of the nurses which in turn affects the quality of nursing care. Emotionally healthy nurse will always perform better. A study conducted with the 180 Dutch nurses using the emotional question inventory Utrecht Burnout scale MMPI 2 and Gamma has revealed that the importance of emotional intelligence in reducing nurse burnout .

Linda (2004.) it is therefore imperative that due to the importance be given to EQ in nursing training and curriculum as it provides the ability to take optimal advantage of ones in eight capabilities by regulating and making use of one's own emotions which would add to the strength of the nursing professionals and bring about qualitative improvement in the area of delivering of the nursing care to the patient as well as their interaction with other members of Healthcare teams the quality of relationships within an organisation significantly impacts productivity and Healthcare organisations are no exception.

Conclusion:

EQ and self-compassion are essential in providing good qualitative nursing care because the compassionate care benefit the patients with regard to the treatment adherence, wound healing ,satisfaction and well-being and it also benefits the positions with regard to lower depression rates ,lower burnouts rates among Healthcare professionals .It also help the nursing students, medical students with regard to their diminished complaints of abusive clinical environment in maladaptive team interactions .Self-compassion consists of the following three components self-kindness perceptions of common humanity and mindfulness. Self -kindness involve extending kindness into oneself instead of self-judgement and criticism .Different research studies evidences that the self-compassion has multiple benefit in the overall personality development of the individual. E.Q also helps to gain awareness and control of one's emotions in the workplace and can improve decision making by using one's heart and not just one's head.

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